

Popular Article

African swine fever: A threat to Indian pigs and food security

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Abstract

African Swine Fever (ASF) is a highly contagious, fatal, re-emerging disease of domestic as well as feral pigs (including wild boar) causing 100% mortality. ASF was first detected in 1921 in Kenya. In India first outbreak of ASF was notified in January 2020 in the North Eastern States of Assam and Arunachal Pradesh. India has a considerable number of small pig holders in rural areas and pork meat is widely consumed by people especially in North Eastern part (NER) of the country. Moreover, pork meat is one of the primary sources of animal proteins, accounting for more than 35% of global meat intake. (FAO Food Outlook 2019). According to the 20th Livestock Census, there are 9.06 million numbers of pigs in the country, which is 1.7% of the total livestock in the country. Pigs are a primary source of household income in many countries. Due to the rapid spreading nature of the disease ASF Virus crosses the boundary and subsequently diseases have been also reported in different districts of Bihar. ASF continues to spread worldwide across Asia, Caribbean, Europe and the pacific regions and responsible for massive losses in pig populations and drastic economic losses. ASF has become a major crisis for pork industry in recent years.

Introduction

African Swine Fever (ASF) is a highly infectious and contagious hemorrhagic viral disease of domestic and feral/wild boar. All breeds, and all ages of pig species are affected. ASF is caused by DNA virus of genus Asfavirus in Asfavididae family. Mortality rate of ASF disease is 100%. All pigs domesticated/captive wild and feral pigs having all age group and breeds are susceptible to the ASF. No other livestock species and human beings are affected with ASF. It is not a danger to human health, but it has devastating effects on pig populations and the farming economy. ASF is a severe threat to pig production system. It is not only threatened to food security and challenges the livelihoods of pig producers and other actors in the supply chain, but may also have affect international trade as a result trade restriction.

Epidemiology

The virus can transmit the disease through blood tissue, secretions and excretions of sick and dead animals. Disease can be transmitted by various modes such as direct transmission via contact with sick and healthy animals and indirect via by feeding of garbage containing ASF infected uncooked meat, fomites like premises, vehicles, equipments and clothes. The virus can persist for up to a month in contaminated pig pens and pork products for over 4 months. Disease may spread through soft tick of genus *Ornithodoros* and acts as a biological vector. Virus may be present in the carcass even if it is a single dead pig for long time and continue to the transmission of disease to the susceptible animal. Clinical symptoms are divided into four forms namely; per-acute, acute, sub-acute and chronic form varies according to different factors such as virulence of virus, route of exposure of disease, infectious dose, breed of swine affected and endemic status in the area. Incubation period in natural infection of disease varies from 4-19 days. In per-acute form pig shows high fever (41-42⁰c) and sudden death within 1-3 days of infection. In acute form pig shows high fever (40-42⁰c) with reddening of the whole skin, bloody secretions from nostril /mouth and bloody diarrhea Mortality rate up to 90-100%. Since there is no vaccine available, reliable and early diagnosis of disease is essential for the implementation of strict sanitary and biosecurity control measures to prevent the spread of disease.

Economic Impact

Across the world, the largest consumed meat is pork. However, in India pork production is only 1.7 % of the total meat production. Consumption of pork is only 2.95 lakh tones in India in 2022. India has 9.06 million of pigs and North Eastern state (NE) states of India are having more than 45% of Indian pig population mostly reared by economically poor people and pork is their staple food. North-eastern States consume more pork compared to other States. But domestic production is unable to meet the growing demand. Recent trends reveal that consumption of pork is increasing in the country. In India, gradually, the trend is moving towards a global consumption pattern taking into account geopolitical situation. OIE reported on May 21, 2020, a total of 11 outbreaks in Assam and Arunachal Pradesh states in India, wherein 3071 pigs were died due to ASF.

Pig production has a lot of challenges in India such as scarcity of superior germplasm, low productivity, conservation of local varieties of pigs, and increasing cost of production and outbreak of emerging disease of pig like African swine fever which may affect the Indian pig industry. Prevention is the only measure as there is no effective vaccine for the disease. Testing of infected

and in-contact pigs, rapid culling of all positive reactors and proper disposal of carcass, litter and infected feed are the way of preventing infection, but that eliminates large no. pigs in the affected area leading to economic losses to pig farmers. Thus, the pig farming can be saved from the threat of this disease by adopting strict biosecurity measures at farm as well as village/surrounding level is to be practiced and initiative should be taken towards rapid containment and focus towards eradication of the disease within the shortest possible time to avoid spread and progression to endemic status.

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